

Prioritizing areas for strategic management against wildfires in the Iberian Peninsula using Pan-European datasets

Criteria and sub-criteria identification

The purpose of this survey is to carry out a preliminary identification of stakeholders' preferences on useful sub-criteria to characterize three criteria groups. It aims to inform prioritization of forested areas to be managed at the Iberian Peninsula level, using Pan-European datasets, in view of the risk of wildfires.

This first survey consists of an evaluation of the opinions of the pre-selected survey participants and will be followed by a second survey to find the relevance of each criterion and sub-criterion.

The objective of making this study a participatory work is to integrate heterogeneous knowledge in highlighting the most important criteria for decision making by involving experts and professionals working on different parts of the FIRE-RES project. The selection of sub-criteria to implement in decision support tools, although based on this participatory process, may eventually have to be adapted to the availability of spatial data (inventory data, infrastructure information, etc.).

The time to complete this survey is between 5 and 10 minutes.

* Indicates required question

Identification and background

Please provide the following information to allow us to make sense of your role in fire management and fire risk mitigation and, if you wish, contact you in the future.

Note on anonymity: Your personal and contact details will not be published anywhere. If any findings from this survey are published, you will never be mentioned by name and your verbatim responses will not be attributed to you personally.

With your permission, we may contact you again for a second survey to define the weights of importance to assign to each criterion and sub-criterion.

1. I consent to being contacted for the purpose of being invited to contribute further to this research. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

2. Email address *

3. Name and surname

4. Please state your affiliation (organization, institution, company, etc.) *

5. Which of the following roles do you feel most identified with for your participation in this work? *

Mark only one oval.

- Firefighter
- Emergency response staff other than firefighter
- Researcher
- Land owner / Land manager
- Forest service / agency
- Technology entrepreneur, startup, SME, etc.
- Public authority representative
- Policymaker
- Insurance industry representative
- Community educator
- Forest Engineer
- Other: _____

6. Which country are you based in? *

Criteria identification

7. 1. Which sub-criteria or types of data / information do you consider are relevant for decision making in the context of wildfire events under the criterion '**Fuels**'? *

Tick all that apply.

- Canopy cover
- Above ground biomass
- Canopy base height
- Vertical continuity
- Canopy bulk density
- Slope
- Elevation
- Other: _____

8. 2. Which sub-criteria or types of data / information do you consider are relevant for decision making in the context of wildfire events under the criterion '**Fire behavior**'? *

Tick all that apply.

- Rate of spread (km/h)
- Flame length (m)
- Fire line intensity (kw/m)
- Spotting distance (m)
- Burn probability (%)
- Conditional flame length (m) - Estimator of the mean Flame Length of the n iterations that burned the pixel
- Flame length probabilities (%) - Variable that represent the probability distribution that several (n) fires with a Flame Length higher than 3m burned that pixel.
- Other: _____

9. 3. Which sub-criteria or types of data / information do you consider are relevant for decision making in the context of wildfire events under the criterion '**Values at risk**'? *

Tick all that apply.

- Population density (people/km²)
- Protected areas
- Carbon stock (tn/ha)
- Proximity to a primary road (m) - Distance from the pixel centroid to the nearest major path
- Other: _____

10. Do you have any comments or suggestions for additional or new sub-criteria that you consider is relevant and we should include in our proposal?

11. Would you be willing to participate after some weeks in a second survey to assign * weights to the selected sub-criteria by doing pairwise comparisons?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

THANK YOU
for your participation!

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